

COMMUNICATION AND INTERACTIVE MARKETING MANAGEMENT THROUGH INTERNET ADVERTISING

Onhi Yulianti Semara¹, Wuri Handayani², Firda Rahayu³, Syahrial Shaddiq⁴

^{1,2,3}Magister Ilmu Komunikasi,
Universitas Islam Kalimantan.
Indonesia.

⁴Manajemen, Universitas Cahaya
Bangsa (yoUCB) Banjarmasin.
Indonesia. Email:
syahrial.shaddiq@mail.ugm.ac.id

*Author's Correspondence:
wurihandayani.st@gmail.com

Abstract

Internet advertising is a development of interactive online marketing communication media that marketers can choose from. The various advantages of internet advertising compared to traditional marketing communication media make this media increasingly used. Social networks or social media have the potential to help SMEs in marketing their products and services (Viral Marketing). Because it is able to reach large areas in a cost-effective manner. Through social networking, SME businesses can carry out marketing activities such as introducing products, establishing communication with customers and potential customers, and expanding business networks. And in its implementation also implements a Customer Relationship Management strategy.

Keywords: Internet Advertising, Viral Marketing, Social Media, Customer Relationship Management

1. INTRODUCTION

The presence of information and communication technology makes the internet inseparable from the daily life of modern humans today. The development of information technology has been responded to by the penetration and behavior of Indonesian internet usage, which has grown from year to year. Internet users in Indonesia in early 2021 reached 202.6 million people. This number increased by 15.5 percent or 27 million people compared to January 2020. The total population of Indonesia itself is currently 274.9 million people. This means internet users in Indonesia in early 2021 will reach 73.7 percent. The development of the number of internet users makes Indonesia one of the great opportunities for business people. Currently, the internet is often used as a medium for shopping and online marketing a product because of the convenience and practicality it offers (Nikmatulloh and Wijayanto, 2021: 837-838).

The popularity of the internet has opened up many opportunities for various

advertisements that can be offered to the public, including Social Networking Sites (SJS), websites, e-mail, videos, widgets, games, pop-ups, instant messaging, and others. Advertising on the internet has advantages over traditional media. The presence of the internet has revolutionized the phenomenon in the history of mass communication technology. Although television received a higher initial acceptance rate than the internet, the number of people who can access the internet increases every year.

The utilization of social networks as internet-based media has the potential as a means of communication and virtual interaction without being limited by space and time. It has excellent potential for SME entrepreneurs to develop their businesses because they can reach a wide area and are cost-effective. Through social networks, SME business players can market their products by sharing information on the latest business activities, sharing product images in

the broader market, building product images in cyberspace, establishing communication with potential customers, and expanding their business network. These business activities can be carried out with minimal costs because the capital required is only an internet network. Thus, it is hoped that the marketing of SME products in the regions will no longer experience obstacles.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Internet Advertising

According to Schlosser and Shavin (1999), the definition of internet advertising is a form of commercial content on the internet designed by businesses to inform consumers about products or services. Internet advertising can be delivered through many channels (e.g., e-mail messages, interactive games, etc.) in various forms (e.g., video clips, print, or audio). According to Strauss and Frost (2009), internet advertising is non-personal communication that is persuasive, communicating about products or ideas by certain sponsors. Jayawardhena et al. (2007) stated that consumers have the choice to use the internet or other traditional media in making purchases. Therefore, marketing practitioners are advised to try digital media on the internet as a development of traditional marketing activities. According to Walmsley (2007), with the increasing volume of activity on the internet and its ability to transform communication media into interactive media, marketers, and consumers are and between consumers (Ramadhani et al., 2021).

When compared with traditional media, the internet is not only a two-way communication medium but is also used for collecting, storing information, receiving orders, and making payments from consumers. These diverse functions make the internet a tool to convey not only marketer messages but also a forum for consumers to increase alternatives in decision making

(Walmsley, 2007; Fadilurrahman et al., 2021). Chaffey (2007) provides various characteristics that make digital media different from traditional media:

1. Internet media can create interactions between marketers and consumers and between consumers.

2. Internet media can bring opportunities for marketers to develop consumer profiles and enable them to further process information. Coupled with the development of Social Networking Sites (SNS), marketers can quickly obtain and disseminate vital information to develop potential consumer profiles.

3. Internet media can communicate with specific individuals personally. This ability is essential in maintaining good customer-based relationships for online marketers because, with personal attention, it can capture consumer desires in a customized and fast manner. Marketers can use the internet to facilitate feedback from consumers on promotions or after-sales services.

4. Digital media on the internet can integrate the functions of other marketing communication tools, audio functions, images, text, animation, and others so that one medium can have rich media properties.

5. The use of the internet as an advertising medium is not limited by location. Marketers have the advantage of virtual access to the whole world, an obstacle for traditional media.

6. With internet advertising, marketers can select specific consumer segments and customize the site according to consumer behavior profiles. According to Chaffey (2007), internet advertising applies the concept of "pull" advertising, allowing consumers to voluntarily learn and compare one brand of goods with other brands more easily and quickly than traditional media. Yaakop and Hemsley-Brown (2013) add that the advantages of the internet allow information on websites to be delivered twenty-four hours a day, seven days a week,

quickly and conveniently by consumers. In addition, advertisers can track the number of visitors to their sites and interact with consumers.

2.2. Variety of Internet Advertising

With the development of digital technology on the internet, marketers can choose various types of advertising offered. However, consumers also have control over digital advertising on the internet because consumers can easily ignore or close the ads they get. Therefore, many digital advertising technologies offer various strategies for advertising messages to reach consumers.

Strauss and Frost (2009) and Laudon (2010) describe various types of internet advertising, including display advertising, rich media, transition and superstitial advertising, e-mail advertising, sponsorship, mobile advertising, and websites. The following is an explanation of each type of internet advertising:

1. Display advertising is a type of advertising that consists of more graphics than text. This type of ad is often called a pop-up. This ad is aimed chiefly at brand awareness;
2. Rich media is a type of advertising that has various types in various formats of choice, including banners, interstitial advertising, floating advertising, wallpaper advertising, trick banners, video advertising, and others;
3. Translation is a type of advertisement which appears when other content is loading (between pages), while superstitial is a kind of mini video advertising that appears when a visitor's mouse moves from one part of the site to another;
4. E-mail advertising is a form of advertising in text format;
5. Sponsorship (advertorial) is a combination of editorial articles with advertisements;
6. Mobile advertising is advertising media with cellular phone media. In addition to internet advertising, online marketing communication media that can be utilized

include Marketing Public Relations (MPR), Sales Promotion, and Direct Marketing (Strauss and Frost, 2009).

2.3. Customer Relationship Management Through Internet Advertising

The importance of internet advertising also supports the concept of Customer Relationship Management (CRM). Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a process for targeting, acquiring, transacting, servicing, retaining, and building long-term relationships with consumers (Strauss and Frost, 2009). These CRM functions can be carried out more easily and quickly by using internet media. For example, with Social Networking Sites, satisfied consumers can recommend websites, online stores, and products to others.

Strauss and Frost (2009) add that Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) among consumers can be said to be the heart of CRM. Positive word of mouth can attract many consumers, but negative word of mouth can make consumers leave the company's products. Word of mouth can quickly spread through e-mail, newsgroups, blogs, social networks, websites, etc.

2.4. Viral Marketing With Social Networking Site Support

The use of the internet as an advertising medium has now undergone an evolution. One of the evolutions in internet advertising in the last five years is social networking sites as part of the promotional mix (Mangoed and Faulds, 2009). The idea of using Social Networking Sites such as Youtube, Facebook, and Twitter to disseminate product information is associated with the ability of these sites to facilitate electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) or viral marketing among consumers.

Porter and Golan (2006) provide an initial definition of viral marketing, namely peer-to-peer communication (between consumers) that is not paid for provocative

content obtained from certain sponsors using the internet to influence audiences to spread messages to others. Porter and Golan (2006) introduced that viral marketing is usually obtained from e-mail lists of loyal consumers or company websites.

Social networking sites such as Facebook allow target consumers to be messengers by sending advertising to friends, linking friends to advertisers explicitly, or commenting on advertisements (Chu, 2011). Facilities in Facebook such as groups are also media to support viral marketing. With Facebook, groups can allow advertisers to send inbox messages to group members. When group members resend viral advertising to other friends, it is as if they become endorsers in product brands advertised on Facebook and increase the desire of other friends to see the ad (Wijaya et al., 2021)

4. CONCLUSION

The internet as a promotional medium is growing and adding alternative options other than traditional media. The various

advantages of the internet compared to traditional media make this media increasingly popular in the eyes of marketers. The popularity of internet marketing has opened many opportunities for various advertisements to the public, including Social Networking Sites (SNS), websites, e-mail, videos, widgets, games, pop-ups, instant messaging, and others. So, nowadays, consumers are not only crammed with traditional media advertisements but also advertisements through internet media. Given the variety and overwhelming volume of advertising that consumers face, it is possible for consumers to ignore ad content or not read advertising messages they do not like. Despite the variety of internet marketing options with various advantages, it is necessary to know how consumers respond to internet marketing and how they impact consumer purchasing decisions. This is done so that the company's investment in this field can be measured and evaluated if there are impacts that have not met the company's targets.

REFERENCE

- Chaffey, D., (2007). *Internet Marketing : Strategy, Implementation and Practice* (4th ed.). Prentice-Hall, England.
- Chu, Shu-Cuan (2011), Viral Marketing In Social Media: Participation in Facebook Group And Responses Among College-Age User, *Journal of Interactive Advertising*.
- Jayawardhena, C., Wright, L.-T., & Dennis, C. (2007), Consumers online: Intentions, Orientations and Segmentation, *International Journal of Retail and Distribution Management*, 35(6).
- Laudon, Kenneth, C., dan Traver, Carol Guercio, (2010) *E-Commerce 2010: Business, Technology, Society*, Pearson, International Edition.
- Mangold, W. G., & Faulds, D. J. (2009). Social Media: The New Hybrid Element of the Promotion Mix, *Business Horizons*, 5(4), 357-365.
- Porter, Lance, and Guy Golan (2006), "From Subservient Chickens to Brawny Men: A Comparison of Viral Advertising to Television Advertising," *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 6 (2)
- Schlosser, A. E., dan Shavitt, S. (1999). Survey of Internet Users' Attitude toward Internet Advertising. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 13(3), 34-54.

- Strauss, Judi, dan Raymond, Frost, (2009), *E-Marketing*, 5th edition, Pearson International Edition.
- Walmsley, A. (2007), New Media: The Age of the Trialogue. *The Marketer*, 12.
- Yaakop, A., dan Hemsley-Brown, Jane (2011), Hedonic Pleasure and Social Image: The Effectiveness of Internet Advertising, *Asian Social Science*, 9 (1).
- A. A. Nikmatulloh, and A. Wijayanto, "Pengaruh Kesadaran Merek, Kepercayaan, Dan Harga Terhadap Minat Beli Online Pada Marketplace Bukalapak (Studi Pada Pengguna Bukalapak Di Kota Semarang)," *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 837-848, Apr. 2021.
- Angga Andaru, Yanu (2016), Pengaruh Iklan Internet, Promosi Penjualan dan *Peer Group* terhadap Minat Beli Produk Fashion pada Toko Fashion Online, *Jurnal Universitas Diponegoro Semarang*.
- Erica Delia Santoso, Novia Larasat. Benarkah Iklan *Online* Efektif Untuk Digunakan Dalam Promosi Perusahaan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Bisnis dan Ekonomi Asia Volume 13 Number 1* , 2019, *Pages* 28-36.
- Fadilurrahman, M., Ramadhani, R., Kurniawan, T., Misnasanti, M., & Shaddiq, S. (2021). Systematic Literature Review of Disruption Era in Indonesia: The Resistance of Industrial Revolution 4.0. *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, 2(1), 51-59.
- Harto, Dedy., Rini Pratiwi., Sulistya., Nur Utomo, Mohamad., Rahmawati, Meylin., (2019) Penerapan Internet Marketing Dalam Meningkatkan Pendapatan Pada UMKM. *Jurnal Pengabdian Dan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. Volume 3 No. 1 Maret 2019*.
- Hery Priyanto, Mukhamad Najib, Stevia, Septiani. Faktor Adopsi *E-Marketing* dan Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Pemasaran UKM Kuliner Kota Bogor, *Jurnal Sistem Informasi Bisnis* 02(2020), DOI: 10.21456/vol10iss2pp235-244.
- Lestari, H., Sunarti, S., & Bafadhal, A. S. (2019). Pengaruh Brand Ambassador Dan Korean Wave Terhadap Citra Merek Serta Dampaknya Pada Keputusan Pembelian (Survei Online Pada Konsumen Innisfree Di Indonesia Dan China). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 66(1), 67-78.
- Nur, Afifah, Aisyah., Najib., Mukhamad., Sarma., Ma'mun. (2018). *Digital Marketing Adoption And The Influences Towards Business Successes Of MSMEs Creative Sector In Inonesia And Malaysia*. *Journal of Applied Management (JAM) Volume 16 Number 3, September 2018 Indexed in Google Scholar*.
- Ramadhani, R., Suswanta, S., & Shaddiq, S. (2021). E-Marketing of Village Tourism Development Strategy (Case Study in the Tourist Village Puncak Sosok). *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, 2(2), 72-77.
- Santi Susanti, Wahyu Gunawan , Sukaesih (2019). Pengembangan pemasaran Bordir Dan Kelom Geulis Tasikmalaya Melalui Media Sosial. *Kumawula*, Vol. 2, No.3, Desember 2019, Hal 248 – 261
- Wijaya, B. A., Noveriady, M., Puspaningratri, N., & Shaddiq, S. (2021). The Role of Corporate Marketing Communications Management in Implementing Advertising Ethics and Standards. *Jurnal Mantik*, 5(2), 807-811.